

Supplementary Information

Scale-up of room-temperature constructive quantum interference from single molecules to self-assembled molecular-electronic films

Xintai Wang^{a,e,†}, Troy L. R. Bennett^{b,†}, Ali Ismael^{a,c,†}, Luke A. Wilkinson^b, Joseph Hamill^d, Andrew J. P. White^b, Iain M. Grace^a, Oleg V. Kolosov^a, Tim Albrecht^d, Benjamin J. Robinson^{a*}, Nicholas J. Long^{b*}, Lesley F. Cohen^{e*} and Colin J. Lambert^{a*}

^aPhysics Department, Lancaster University, Lancaster, LA1 4YB, UK.

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Imperial College London, MSRH, White City, London, W12 0BZ, UK.

^cDepartment of Physics, College of Education for Pure Science, Tikrit University, Tikrit, Iraq.

^dDepartment of Chemistry, Birmingham University, Edgbaston, Birmingham, B15 2TT, UK.

^eThe Blackett Laboratory, Imperial College London, South Kensington Campus, London, SW7 2AZ, UK.

[†]These authors contributed equally to this work

*To whom correspondence should be addressed. e-mail: c.lambert@lancaster.ac.uk; l.cohen@imperial.ac.uk; n.long@imperial.ac.uk; b.j.robinson@lancaster.ac.uk

1. Molecular Synthesis

1.1 Materials and Methods

All reactions were performed with the use of standard air-sensitive chemistry and Schlenk line techniques, under an atmosphere of nitrogen. No special precautions were taken to exclude air during any work-ups. All commercially available reagents were used as received from suppliers, without further purification. 4-Ethynylthioanisole, 4-(ethynyl)phenyl-*tert*-butylthioether and 1,5-dibromoanthracene were synthesised through adapted literature procedures.¹⁻³ Solvents used in reactions were collected from solvent towers sparged with nitrogen and dried with 3 Å molecular sieves, apart from DIPA, which was distilled onto activated 3 Å molecular sieves under nitrogen.

1.2 Instrumentation

¹H and ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance 400 MHz spectrometer and referenced to the residual solvent peaks of CDCl₃ at 7.26 and 77.16 ppm, respectively. Coupling constants are measured in Hz. Mass spectrometry analyses were conducted by Dr. Lisa Haigh of the Mass Spectrometry Service, Imperial College London. Crystal structure analyses were

conducted by Dr. Andrew White of the Crystallography Service, Imperial College London. Infrared spectra were recorded on a PerkinElmer Spectrum FT-IR spectrometer.

1.3 Synthesis

General procedure for the coupling of terminal alkynes to bromoanthracenes – specific details regarding molar equivalents and column conditions are reported below.

This synthetic procedure is adapted from a published method for Sonogashira coupling.⁴ A Schlenk tube was charged with dibromoanthracene, terminal alkyne, CuI (5 mol%) and Pd(P-^tBu₃)₂ (5 mol%) then placed under an inert atmosphere. Anhydrous DIPA and toluene were added to the reaction vessel via cannula and the reaction was stirred overnight at room temperature to generate a bright orange/yellow precipitate. Removal of the solvent *in vacuo* led to a dark brown crude material which can be purified by column chromatography.

9,10-Di(4-(ethynyl)thioanisole)anthracene (**1**)⁵

4-(Ethynyl)thioanisole (0.20 g, 1.35 mmol), 9,10-dibromoanthracene (1.81 g, 5.40 mmol), CuI (0.01 g, 0.07 mmol) and Pd(P-^tBu₃)₂ (0.03 g, 0.07 mmol) gave an orange-brown solid which was purified by chromatography on a silica column, eluted with *n*-hexane/THF (1:0 → 1:1 v/v) to give the product as an orange solid (0.20 g, 0.85 mmol, 63%).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 298 K, 400 MHz): δ_H = 8.69 (dd, ³J_{H-H} = 6.8, ⁴J_{H-H} = 3.2 Hz, 4H, H10), 7.70 (d, ³J_{H-H} = 8.4 Hz, 4H, H4), 7.67 (dd, ³J_{H-H} = 6.8, ⁴J_{H-H} = 3.2 Hz, 4H, H11), 7.32 (d, ³J_{H-H} = 8.4 Hz, 4H, H3), 2.55 (s, 6H, H1) ppm; ¹³C {¹H} NMR (CDCl₃, 298 K, 100 MHz): δ_C = 140.2 (Ar-C-C), 132.2 (Ar-C-C), 132.1 (Ar-C-H), 127.4 (Ar-C-H), 126.9 (Ar-C-H), 126.2 (Ar-C-H), 119.8 (Ar-C-C), 118.6 (Ar-C-C), 102.5 (-C≡C-), 86.9 (-C≡C-), 15.6 (S-CH₃) ppm; IR: 2195 (-C≡C-) cm⁻¹; MS ES+: calcd. for C₃₂H₂₂S₂ [M]⁺ 469.1079; found. 469.1077.

Figure S1: The ¹H NMR spectrum of **1** in CDCl₃

Figure S2: The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **1** in CDCl_3

1,5-Di(4-(ethynyl)thioanisole)anthracene (**2**)

4-(Ethynyl)thioanisole (0.15 g, 1.01 mmol), 1,5-dibromoanthracene (0.10 g, 0.30 mmol), CuI (0.01 g, 0.03 mmol) and $\text{Pd}(\text{P-}^t\text{Bu}_3)_2$ (0.02 g, 0.03 mmol) gave an orange-brown solid which was purified by chromatography on a silica column, eluted with *n*-hexane/THF (1:0 \rightarrow 1:1 v/v) to give the product as an orange solid (0.11 g, 0.24 mmol, 79%).

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 400 MHz): $\delta_{\text{H}} = 8.99$ (s, 2H, *H13*), 8.10 (dd, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 4.4$, $^4J_{\text{HH}} = 1.6$ Hz, 2H, *H9*), 7.80 (dd, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 6.8$, $^4J_{\text{HH}} = 1.2$ Hz, 2H, *H11*), 7.63 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.0$ Hz, 4H, *H4*), 7.55-7.45 (m, 2H, *H10*), 7.30 (d, $^3J_{\text{HH}} = 8.0$ Hz, 4H, *H3*), 2.55 (s, 6H, *H1*) ppm; $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 100 MHz): $\delta_{\text{C}} = 139.8$ (Ar-C-C), 132.1 (Ar-C-H), 131.4 (Ar-C-C), 130.7 (Ar-C-H), 129.6 (Ar-C-H), 126.1 (Ar-C-H), 125.9 (Ar-C-H), 125.3 (Ar-C-H), 121.1 (Ar-C-C), 119.8 (Ar-C-C), 94.9 (-C \equiv C-), 87.9 (-C \equiv C-), 15.6 (S-CH $_3$) ppm; IR: 2207 (-C \equiv C-) cm^{-1} ; MS ES+: calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{22}\text{S}_2$ [M] $^+$ 469.1074; found. 469.1081.

Figure S3: The ^1H NMR spectrum of **2** in CDCl_3

Figure S4: The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **2** in CDCl_3

9,10-Di(4-(ethynyl)phenyl-*tert*-butylthioether)anthracene (3A**)²**

9,10-Dibromoanthracene (0.15 g, 0.45 mmol), 4-(ethynyl)phenyl-*tert*-butylthioether (0.21 g, 1.12 mmol), CuI (0.01 g, 0.05 mmol) and $\text{Pd}(\text{P-}^i\text{Bu}_3)_2$ (0.02 g, 0.05 mmol) gave an orange-brown solid which was purified by chromatography on a silica column, eluting with *n*-hexane/DCM (1:0→8:2) to give the product as an orange solid (0.19 g, 0.34 mmol, 76%).

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 400 MHz): $\delta_{\text{H}} = 8.72\text{--}8.67$ (m, 4H, *H*11), 7.74 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 4H, *H*5), 7.68–7.63 (m, 4H, *H*12), 7.63 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 4H, *H*4), 1.35 (s, 18H, *H*1) ppm; $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 100 MHz): $\delta_{\text{C}} = 137.6$ (Ar-C-H), 134.0 (Ar-C-C), 132.3 (Ar-C-C), 131.7 (Ar-C-H), 127.4 (Ar-C-H), 127.1 (Ar-C-H), 123.9 (Ar-C-C), 118.6 (Ar-C-C), 102.1 (-C≡C-), 88.1 (-C≡C-), 46.8 (S-C-C), 31.2 (CH_3) ppm; IR: 2194 (-C≡C-) cm^{-1} ; MS APCI: calcd. $[\text{M}]^+555.2175$; found. 555.2171.

Figure S5: The ^1H NMR spectrum of **3A** in CDCl_3

Figure S6: The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **3A** in CDCl_3

9,10- Di(4-(ethynyl)phenylthioacetate)anthracene (**3**)²

Synthesised according to an adapted literature procedure.² (**3A**) (0.08 g, 0.14 mmol) was dissolved in DCM (30 mL) and toluene (30 mL). Acetyl chloride (1 mL) was added and the solution was degassed for 20 minutes. BBr_3 (1 M in hexanes, 0.72 mL, 0.72 mmol) was added and the solution was stirred overnight at room temperature. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the crude product was exposed to chromatography on a silica column, eluting with *n*-hexane/DCM (1:0 \rightarrow 1:1). The product was washed with hexane (3 x 100 mL) and recrystallized from DCM to yield dark orange crystals (0.03 g, 0.06 mmol, 43%).

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 400 MHz) δ_{H} = 8.71-8.64 (m, 4H, *H*11), 7.81 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 4H, *H*5), 7.69-7.62 (m, 4H, *H*12), 7.51 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 4H, *H*4), 2.48 (s, 6H, *H*1) ppm; $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 100 MHz): δ_{C} = 193.4 (-C=O), 134.4 (Ar-C-H), 132.2 (Ar-C-H), 132.2 (Ar-C-C), 128.6 (Ar-C-C), 127.2 (Ar-C-H), 127.0 (Ar-C-H), 124.6 (Ar-C-C), 118.4 (Ar-C-C), 101.7 (-C \equiv C-), 88.1 (-C \equiv C-), 30.4 (CH_3) ppm; IR: 2195 (-C \equiv C-), 1692 (-C=O) cm^{-1} ; MS ES+: calcd. $[\text{M}]^+$ 527.1134; found. 527.1128.

Figure S7: The ^1H NMR spectrum of **3B** in CDCl_3

Figure S8: The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **3B** in CDCl_3

1,5- Di(4-(ethynyl)phenyl-*tert*-butylthioether)anthracene (**4A**)

Synthesised according to an adapted literature procedure.² 1,5-Dibromoanthracene (0.15 g, 0.45 mmol), 4-(ethynyl)phenyl-*tert*-butylthioether (0.21 g, 1.12 mmol), CuI and Pd($\text{P}^t\text{-Bu}_3$)₂ (0.02 g, 0.05 mmol) gave a yellow-brown solid which was purified by chromatography on a silica column, eluting with *n*-hexane/DCM (1:0 → 4:1) to give the product as a yellow solid (0.22 g, 0.39 mmol, 87%).

^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 400 MHz): $\delta_{\text{H}} = 9.00$ (s, 2H, *H*14), 8.13 (dd, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 4.4$, $^4J_{\text{H-H}} = 1.6$ Hz, 4H, *H*10), 7.82 (dd, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 6.8$, $^4J_{\text{H-H}} = 1.2$ Hz, 2H, *H*12), 7.68 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 4H, *H*5) 7.61 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 4H, *H*4), 7.53-

7.48 (m, 2H, *H*11), 1.34 (s, 18H, *H*1) ppm; $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 100 MHz): δ_{C} = 137.5 (Ar-C-H), 133.7 (Ar-C-C), 131.8 (Ar-C-H), 131.8 (Ar-C-H), 131.4 (Ar-C-C), 130.9 (Ar-C-H), 129.9 (Ar-C-C), 125.9 (Ar-C-C), 125.4 (Ar-C-H), 123.9 (Ar-C-C), 120.9 (Ar-C-C), 94.5 (-C \equiv C-), 89.3 (-C \equiv C-), 46.8 (S-C-), 31.2 (CH_3) ppm; IR: 2202 (-C \equiv C-) cm^{-1} ; MS APCI: calcd. $[\text{M}]^+555.2175$; found. 555.2173.

Figure S9: The ^1H NMR spectrum of **4A** in CDCl_3

Figure S10: The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **4A** in CDCl_3

1,5- Di(4-(ethynyl)phenylthioacetate)anthracene (**4**)

Synthesised according to an adapted literature procedure.² (**4A**) (0.08 g, 0.14 mmol) was dissolved in DCM (30 mL) and toluene (30 mL). Acetyl chloride (1 mL) was added and the solution was degassed for 20 minutes. BBr_3 (1 M in hexanes, 0.72 mL, 0.72 mmol) was added and the solution was stirred overnight at room

temperature. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the crude product was exposed to chromatography on a silica column, eluting with chloroform to give the product as a yellow solid (0.05 g, 0.09 mmol, 63%).

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 400 MHz): $\delta_{\text{H}} = 8.98$ (s, 2H, *H*14), 8.13 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 4.4$ Hz, 2H, *H*10), 7.81 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 4.4$ Hz, 2H, *H*12), 7.75 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 2H, *H*5), 7.54-7.49 (m, 6H, *H*4/11), 7.49 (d, $^3J_{\text{H-H}} = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 2.47 (s, 6H) ppm; **$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR** (CDCl_3 , 298 K, 100 MHz): $\delta_{\text{C}} = 193.6$ (-C=O), 134.5 (Ar-C-H), 132.5 (Ar-C-H), 131.8 (Ar-C-C), 131.4 (Ar-C-H), 131.1 (Ar-C-C), 130.1 (Ar-C-H), 128.5 (Ar-C-C), 125.9 (Ar-C-H), 125.4 (Ar-C-H), 124.8 (Ar-C-C), 120.7 (Ar-C-C), 94.2 (-C \equiv C-), 89.4 (-C \equiv C-), 30.5 (CH_3) ppm; **IR**: 2204 (-C \equiv C-), 1687 (-C=O) cm^{-1} ; **MS ES+**: calcd. $[\text{M}]^+$ 527.1134; found. 527.1114.

Figure S11: The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum of **4B** in CDCl_3

Figure S12: The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of **4B** in CDCl_3

1.4 Crystallographic Information

The X-ray crystal structure of **1**

Crystal data for 1: $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{22}\text{S}_2$, $M = 470.61$, monoclinic, $P2_1/c$ (no. 14), $a = 5.2790(5)$, $b = 8.0061(9)$, $c = 28.485(3)$ Å, $\beta = 90.732(9)^\circ$, $V = 1203.8(2)$ Å³, $Z = 2$ [C_i symmetry], $D_c = 1.298$ g cm^{-3} , $\mu(\text{Mo-K}\alpha) = 0.240$ mm^{-1} , $T = 173$ K, orange platy needles, Agilent Xcalibur 3 E diffractometer; 2437 independent measured reflections ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0285$), F^2 refinement,^{6,7} $R_1(\text{obs}) = 0.0538$, $wR_2(\text{all}) = 0.1280$, 1795 independent observed absorption-corrected reflections [$|F_o| > 4\sigma(|F_o|)$], completeness to $\theta_{\text{full}}(25.2^\circ) = 99.8\%$, 156 parameters. CCDC 1944032.

The structure of **1** was found to sit across a centre of symmetry at the middle of the anthracenyl moiety.

Figure S13: The crystal structure of the C_i -symmetric molecule **1** (50% probability ellipsoids).

The X-ray crystal structure of **3**

Crystal data for 3: $C_{34}H_{22}O_2S_2$, $M = 526.63$, triclinic, $P-1$ (no. 2), $a = 5.0612(10)$, $b = 9.591(2)$, $c = 13.810(2)$ Å, $\alpha = 98.634(15)$, $\beta = 90.898(14)$, $\gamma = 101.338(18)^\circ$, $V = 649.1(2)$ Å³, $Z = 1$ [C_i symmetry], $D_c = 1.347$ g cm⁻³, $\mu(\text{Mo-K}\alpha) = 0.236$ mm⁻¹, $T = 173$ K, orange blocky needles, Agilent Xcalibur 3 E diffractometer; 2554 independent measured reflections ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0229$), F^2 refinement,^{6,7} $R_1(\text{obs}) = 0.0437$, $wR_2(\text{all}) = 0.0993$, 1923 independent observed absorption-corrected reflections [$|F_o| > 4\sigma(|F_o|)$], completeness to $\theta_{\text{full}}(25.2^\circ) = 98.7\%$], 174 parameters. CCDC 1958589.

The structure of **3** was found to sit across a centre of symmetry at the middle of the anthracenyl moiety.

Figure S14: The crystal structure of the C_i -symmetric molecule **3** (50% probability ellipsoids).

The X-ray crystal structure of **3A**

Crystal data for 3A: $C_{38}H_{34}S_2$, $M = 554.77$, monoclinic, $C2$ (no. 5), $a = 27.0814(8)$, $b = 5.9789(2)$, $c = 18.7842(6)$ Å, $\beta = 97.344(3)^\circ$, $V = 3016.54(18)$ Å³, $Z = 4$, $D_c = 1.222$ g cm⁻³, $\mu(\text{Cu-K}\alpha) = 1.774$ mm⁻¹, $T = 203$ K, orange platy needles, Agilent Xcalibur PX Ultra A diffractometer; 4200 independent measured reflections ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0221$), F^2 refinement,^{6,7} $R_1(\text{obs}) = 0.0414$, $wR_2(\text{all}) = 0.1063$, 3416 independent observed absorption-corrected reflections [$|F_o| > 4\sigma(|F_o|)$], completeness to $\theta_{\text{full}}(67.7^\circ) = 97.6\%$], 368 parameters. The structure of **3A** was refined as a two-component inversion twin [Flack parameter $x = 0.46(2)$]. CCDC 1958590.

Figure S15: The crystal structure of **3A** (50% probability ellipsoids).

The X-ray crystal structure of **4A**

Crystal data for 4A: $C_{38}H_{34}S_2$, $M = 554.77$, triclinic, $P-1$ (no. 2), $a = 5.9983(6)$, $b = 10.9346(10)$, $c = 11.9346(11)$ Å, $\alpha = 95.669(7)$, $\beta = 97.009(8)$, $\gamma = 93.405(8)^\circ$, $V = 771.11(13)$ Å³, $Z = 1$ [C_i symmetry], $D_c = 1.195$ g cm⁻³, $\mu(\text{Cu-K}\alpha) = 1.735$ mm⁻¹, $T = 203$ K, yellow plates, Agilent Xcalibur PX Ultra A diffractometer; 2914 independent measured reflections ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0370$), F^2 refinement,⁶ $R_1(\text{obs}) = 0.0437$, $wR_2(\text{all}) = 0.1226$, 2182 independent observed absorption-corrected reflections [$|F_o| > 4\sigma(|F_o|)$], completeness to $\theta_{\text{full}}(67.7^\circ) = 98.0\%$, 184 parameters. CCDC 1958591.

The structure of **4A** was found to sit across a centre of symmetry at the middle of the anthracenyl moiety.

Figure S16: The crystal structure of the C_i -symmetric molecule **4A** (50% probability ellipsoids)

2. DFT and Transport Calculations

The ground state Hamiltonian and optimized geometry of each molecule was obtained using the density functional theory (DFT) code.⁸ The local density approximation (LDA) exchange correlation functional was used along with double zeta polarized (DZP) basis sets and the norm conserving pseudo potentials. The real space grid was defined by a plane wave cut-off

of 250 Ry. The geometry optimization was carried out to a force tolerance of 0.01 eV/Å. This process was repeated for a unit cell with the molecule between gold electrodes where the optimized distance between Au and the pyridine anchor group was found to be 2.3 Å, whereas Au and SMe 2.7 Å. From the ground state Hamiltonian, the transmission coefficient, the room temperature electrical conductance G and Seebeck coefficient S was obtained, as described in the sections below. We model the properties of a single molecule in the junction as previous works⁹ have shown the calculated conductance of a SAM differs only slightly from that of single molecules

2.1 Optimised DFT Structures of Isolated Molecules

Using the density functional code SIESTA,^{8, 10} the optimum geometries of the isolated molecules **1-4** were obtained by relaxing the molecules until all forces on the atoms were less than 0.01 eV / Å as shown in Figure S17. A double-zeta plus polarization orbital basis set, norm-conserving pseudopotentials, an energy cut-off of 250 Rydbergs defined the real space grid were used and the local density approximation (LDA) was chosen to be the exchange correlation functional. We also computed results using GGA and found that the resulting transmission functions were comparable with those obtained using LDA.^{11, 12}

Figure S17: Fully relaxed isolated molecules. Key: C = grey, H = white, O = red, S = yellow.

2.2 Frontier orbitals of the molecules

The plots below show isosurfaces of the HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 of isolated molecules 1-4.

Figure S18: Wave function for 1. Top panel: Fully optimised geometry of 1. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 along with their energies

Figure S19: Wave function for 2. Top panel: Fully optimised geometry of 2. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 along with their energies

Figure S20: Wave function for **3**. Top panel: Fully optimized geometry of **3**. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 along with their energies

Figure S21: Wave function for **4**. Top panel: Fully optimized geometry of **4**. Lower panel: HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 along with their energies.

2.3 Product rule

Wave function plots for isolated molecules with their optimised geometries (Figures S18-S21) show iso-surfaces of the HOMO, LUMO, HOMO-1 and LUMO+1 of isolated molecules of the studied molecules. The information of the product rule¹³⁻¹⁵ is obtained from Figures S18-S21. Product rule predicts a CQI in the HOMO-LUMO gap for the molecules of study, because the product of the HOMO (LUMO) amplitudes at opposite ends of the molecules is negative (positive). Table S1 summarises the signs of these orbital products.

Table S1: Product rule predictions of the studied molecules, (c= constructive, d=destructive, blue= -ive and red= +ive).

Compound	H-1	H	L	L+1	G _{H-L}
1	+	-	+	-	c
E (eV)	-4.73	-4.02	-2.39	-1.28	
2	+	-	+	-	c
E (eV)	-4.48	-4.18	-2.24	-1.71	
3	+	-	+	-	c
E (eV)	-5.31	-4.62	-3.11	-1.95	
4	-	-	+	-	c
E (eV)	-5.01	-4.59	-3.13	-1.95	

2.4 Binding energy of molecules on Au

To calculate the optimum binding distance between pyridyl/thioether anchor groups and Au(111) surfaces, we used DFT and the counterpoise method, which removes basis set superposition errors (BSSE). The binding distance d is defined as the distance between the gold surface and the S/SMe terminus of the thiol/methyl sulphide group. Here, compound **1** is defined as entity A and the gold electrode as entity B. The ground state energy of the total system is calculated using SIESTA and is denoted E_{AB}^{AB} . The energy of each entity is then calculated in a fixed basis, which is achieved using ghost atoms in SIESTA. Hence, the energy of the individual **1** in the presence of the fixed basis is defined as E_A^{AB} and for the gold as E_B^{AB} . The binding energy is then calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Binding Energy} = E_{AB}^{AB} - E_A^{AB} - E_B^{AB} \quad (\text{S1})$$

We then considered the nature of the binding depending on the gold surface structure. We calculated the binding to a Au pyramid on a surface with the thioether sulphide atom binding at a 'top' site and then varied the binding distance d . Figure S22 (left) shows that a value of $d = 2.4 \text{ \AA}$ gives the optimum distance, at approximately 0.8 eV. As expected, the thiol anchor group binds favourably to under-coordinated gold atoms. For SMe $d = 2.7 \text{ \AA}$ gives the optimum distance, at approximately 0.5 eV.

Figure S22: Example binding energy plot of **4**, for two different anchors Au-S and Au-SMe (left), with its idealised ad-atom configuration at the Au lead interface (right, top Au-S and bottom Au-SMe).

Key: C = grey, H = white, S = light yellow, Au = dark yellow.

2.5 Optimised DFT Structures of Compounds in Their Junctions

Using the optimised structures and geometries for the compounds obtained as described in section 2.1 (above), we again employed the SIESTA code to calculate self-consistent optimised geometries, ground state Hamiltonians and overlap matrix elements for each metal-molecule-metal junction. Leads were modelled as 625 atom slabs, terminated with 11-atom Au(111) tips. The optimised structures were then used to compute the transmission curve for each compound. The DFT optimised geometries are shown here, in Figures S23-26. Note: there is a tilt angle range for each compound, which presents in section 2.5.

Key: C = grey, H = white, S = light yellow, Au = dark yellow.

Figure S23: Optimised structure of **1**.

Figure S24: Optimised structure of **2**.

Figure S25: Optimised structure of **3**.

Figure S26: Optimised structure of **4**.

2.6 The tilt angle (θ)

In this section, we determine the tilt angle θ of each compound on a gold substrate, which corresponds to the experimentally measured most-probable break-off distance. In previous work⁹ we have demonstrated how the tilt angle calculates for both single molecule and SAM. Table S2 shows each compound for a range of tilt angles. Break-off distance values suggest that compound-**1** and **-2** tilt with angle θ ranging from 51° to 59° , compound-**3** 29° - 33° and compound-**4** 27° - 35°

Table S2: Experimental break-off distance and equivalent tilt angle (θ)

Compound	Experimental film thickness (nm)	Experimental film roughness (nm)	Equivalent experimental tilt angle (θ)	Equivalent theoretical tilt angle (θ)
1	1.25	0.17	51° - 59°	51° - 59°
2	1.28	0.11	51° - 59°	51° - 59°
3	1.12	0.13	29° - 33°	29° - 33°
4	1.19	0.09	27° - 35°	27° - 35°

Figure S27: Optimised structures of **1-4**. Tilt angle (side-view)

2.7 HOMO-LUMO gaps

The calculated and optically measured HOMO-LUMO gaps are listed in Table S3. Theoretical gaps were calculated for isolated molecules and when the compounds are placed in the junctions, the gap between their HOMO and LUMO transmission resonances are quoted. As shown by the third and fourth columns in Table S2, isolated gaps for compounds **1**, **2**, **3** and **4** are larger than the gaps between the transmission resonances. This is because the latter are shifted by the real part of the self-energy of the contact to the leads, reflecting the fact that the system is more open when contacted to electrodes. In general, theoretical gaps are smaller than the measured gaps, which is consistent with the fact that DFT is known to underestimate its value.^{16, 17}

Table S3: Experimental and theoretical HOMO–LUMO gaps in eV.

Compound	E _g , (Exp.) ^a	E _g , DFT (Iso.) ^b	E _g , DFT (Au-M-Au) ^c
1	2.57	1.63	1.30
2	3.75	1.94	1.85
3	2.66	1.51	1.20
4	2.61	1.46	1.25

^a Experimental data: $E_g = 1241.5/\lambda_{\text{ABS}}$. ^b Theoretical HOMO–LUMO gaps for the isolated molecules. ^c Theoretical gaps between HOMO–LUMO transmission resonances in Au|molecule|Au structures.

2.8 Transport Calculations

The transmission coefficient curves $T(E)$, obtained from using the Gollum transport code, were calculated for compounds **1-4** based on the tilt angle range in Table S2. The LUMO resonance is predicted to be pinned near the Fermi Level of the electrodes for the four molecules, however, we choose Fermi Level to be in the mid gap at approximately ± 0.5 eV (black-dashed line), as shown in Figure S28.

Figure S28: Zero bias transmission coefficient $T(E)$ of molecules **1-4** against electron energy E . **Left panel:** compound **1** (red-lines), compound **2** (blue-line). **Right panel:** compound **3** (green-line), and compound **4** (black-line), yellow-lines the average of each compound.

In previous works⁹ we have demonstrated that the transmission coefficient $T(E)$, for single molecule is approximately the same for SAM, by comparing $T(E)$ for single molecule against SAM consists of 7 molecules.

2.9 Seebeck coefficient

After covering the electronic transport for the four molecules, the study of some thermoelectronic properties such as thermopower S for the same groups is made.

To calculate the thermopower of these molecular junctions, it is useful to introduce the non-normalised probability distribution $P(E)$ defined by

$$P(E) = -\mathcal{T}(E) \frac{df(E)}{dE} \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $f(E)$ is the Fermi-Dirac function and $\mathcal{T}(E)$ are the transmission coefficients and whose moments L_i are denoted as follows

$$L_i = \int dE P(E) (E - E_F)^i \quad (\text{S3})$$

where E_F is the Fermi energy. The thermopower, S , is then given by

$$S(T) = -\frac{1}{|e|T} \frac{L_1}{L_0} \quad (\text{S4})$$

where e is the electronic charge.

Supplementary Figure S29 shows the thermopower S evaluated at room temperature for different energy range $E_F - E_F^{\text{DFT}}$.

Figure S29: Seebeck coefficient S of the same molecules. **Left panel:** (1 and 2), **Right panel:** (3 and 4)

2.10 Magic number table for anthracene core

To demonstrate that conductances are not simply a reflection of the path lengths between injection and collection points, it is useful to examine the full magic number table for the anthracene core, which is shown below. This captures the effect of connectivity by noting that if electrons are injected at pi orbital i and collected at pi orbital j , then the electrical conductance, then the contribution to electrical conductance from the pi system of the core is proportional to $(M_{ij})^2$, where M_{ij} is the i, j th entry in the magic number table. The diagonal blocks (coloured yellow) in this table correspond to DQI, whereas the off-diagonal block correspond to CQI. In the case of CQI, $M_{71'}$ is greater than $M_{62'}$, even though the distances between 7 and 1' is the same as the distance between 6 and 2'. This demonstrates that connectivity dependence of electrical conductances is not simply a reflection of the distances between sites. This lack of correlation with the distances between sites is even more clear when one notes that the entries in the diagonal blocks between unprimed and unprimed numbered sites (such as M_{12}), or primed and primed numbered sites (such

as $M_{1'2'}$) are zero, which demonstrates that even though these are close to each other, their conductances are lower than those between more distant sites, such as $M_{72'}$.

Table S4: Magic Number Table M_{ij} for anthracene core

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1'	2'	3'	4'	5'	6'	7'
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3	2	-1	1	-1	1	-1
2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-2	1	-1	1	-1	1
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-2	-1	1	-1	1	-1
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	2	-3	-1	1	-1	1
5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-2	3	-3	-1	1	-1
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-2	4	-2	2	-2	-2	2
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	-2	1	-1	1	-1	-3
1'	-3	-1	1	-1	1	-2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2'	2	-2	-2	2	-2	4	-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3'	-1	1	-1	-3	3	-2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4'	1	-1	1	-1	-3	2	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5'	-1	1	-1	1	-1	-2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6'	1	-1	1	-1	1	-2	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7'	-1	1	-1	1	-1	2	-3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

3. Characterisation

3.1 QCM monitoring of SAMs growth

The QCM substrate (International Crystal Manufacturing, USA) was rinsed by acetone (>99%), methanol (>99%) and iso-propanol (>99%) in series and cleaned by oxygen plasma for 5 minutes. The stabilised, initial resonance frequency (f_0) of the cleaned QCM substrate was recorded. The cleaned QCM substrate was then immersed in 1 mM solution of molecules **1-4** in 1:2 ethanol:THF mixture (>99.9%, bubbling with nitrogen for 20 min to remove oxygen) from 12 hours to 48 hours. Optimised assembly times were established over multiple depositions. The substrate was subsequently rinsed by THF and ethanol several times to remove excess physisorbed molecules before drying in vacuum (10^{-2} mbar, 40°C). The frequency of substrate after SAMs growth was again measured by the QCM. The equivalent measurement, where the QCM substrate was immersed in 1:2 ethanol:THF mixture without any molecules **1-4** present was also pre-formed as a reference. The difference between the measured frequency and initial frequency, Δf , related with the amount of molecule on Au surface is given by the Sauerbrey equation:

$$n = \frac{-\Delta f \times A \times k \times N_A}{M_w} \quad (S5)$$

$$k = \frac{\sqrt{\mu \cdot \rho}}{2 \cdot f_0^2} \quad (S6)$$

Where n the amount of molecule adsorbed on Au surface, A the electrode area, N_A the Avogadro's number, M_w the molecular weight, μ the shear modulus of quartz, ρ the density of quartz, f_0 the initial frequency.

The single molecular occupation area on Au surface can be calculated by:

$$A_{molecule} = \frac{A_{Electrode}}{n} \quad (S7)$$

the corresponding results were listed in Table S3.

3.2 TS gold preparation for SPM

A Si wafer (5 mm x 5 mm) was cleaned in an ultra-sonication bath with acetone, methanol and isopropanol in series, before cleaning with oxygen plasma for 5 minutes. The cleaned wafer was glued onto the top surface of a thermal evaporated gold sample previously grown on Si (100 nm thickness) with Epotek 353nd epoxy adhesive to form Si/Glue/Au/Si sandwich structure. The adhesive was cured for 40 minutes at 150 °C, then the original, bottom Si substrate was carefully removed using a sharp blade leaving an atomically-flat Au surface which was templated on the original Si surface. The prepared gold was scanned by AFM for 3-5 random spots for quality tests. For all cases, only the substrates with roughness below 0.2 nm were used for SAMs growth.

3.3 SAMs Growth

Following the optimised procedure for QCM, the gold was immersed in solution immediately after cleavage without any further treatment for 12 h (molecules **1**, **2** and **4**) and 24 h (molecule **3**). The substrates were rinsed after molecular assembly by ThF and ethanol and dried in vacuum for 12 hours (10^{-2} mbar, 40 °C).

3.4 Single molecular conductance calculation

The plot of dI/dV (S) vs. bias voltage was shown in Figure S26. The number of molecules contacted by the probe was calculated using contact area between sample and probe dividing the occupation area of a single molecule. The contact area between sample and probe was estimated by Hertzian model:

$$r = \left(F \times R \times \frac{1}{Y} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$
$$\frac{1}{Y} = \frac{3}{4} \times \left(\frac{1 - \nu_1^2}{E_1} + \frac{1 - \nu_2^2}{E_2} \right)$$

Where r the contact radius, F the loading force from probe to sample, R the radius of the probe (~ 10 nm from the supplier), ν_1 and ν_2 the Poisson ratio of the material, E_1 and E_2 the Young's Modulus for probe (~ 100 GPa) and SAMs (~ 10 GPa, estimated by nano-mechanical mapping under peak force mode).

Figure S30: (a-d) AFM topography of molecules **1-4** SAMs after nano-scratching by AFM probe. (e-h) Height profile for (a-d) correspondingly.

3.5 SAMs characterization

SAM topography was characterized by AFM (MultiMode 8, Bruker Nanoscience) in peak force mode, a low force intermittent-contact mode with combines high resolution imaging, sample nanomechanical information and low sample damage. The peak force setpoint was set to the range of 500 pN to 1 nN and the scan rate was set to 1 Hz. The nano-scratching was performed in contact mode at high set force ($F = 15 - 40$ nN) using a soft probe (Multi-75-G, $k = 3$ N/m) to 'sweep away' the molecular film from a defined area ($A = 300$ nm x 300 nm). The topography of sample after scratching was again characterized in peak force mode, the scratched window is easily observed. Nano-scratching was also conducted on a bare gold sample under the same conditions to ensure no gold is scratched away in used force range. The height difference between the scratched part and un-scratched part indicates the thickness of SAMs.

3.6 Conductive AFM (cAFM)

The electrical transport properties of the SAMs were characterized by a custom cAFM system. The cAFM setup is based on a multi-mode8 AFM system (Bruker nanoscience). The bottom gold substrate was used as the source, and a Pt/Cr coated probe (Multi75 E, BudgetSensor) was used as the drain. The force between probe and molecule was controlled at 2 nN, as this force is strong enough for the probe to penetrate through the water layer on the sample surface but not too strong to destroy the molecular thin film. The driven bias was added between the source and drain by a voltage generator (Aglient 33500B), the source to drain current was amplified by a current pre-amplifier (SR570, Stanford Research Systems), and the IV characteristics of the sample was collected by the computer.

3.7 Thermal-Electrical Atomic Force Microscopy (ThEFM)

The Seebeck coefficients of SAMs were obtained by a ThEFM modified from the cAFM system used for electrical transport measurement. A peltier stage driven by a voltage generator (Aglient 33500B, voltage amplified by a wide band amplifier) was used to heat up and cool, thus a temperature difference can be created between sample and probe. The sample temperature was measured by a Type T thermal couple, and the probe temperature was calibrated by using an SThM (scanning thermal microscopy) probe (KNT SThM 2an) under the same conditions ($F = 2$ nN). We made an assumption that the SThM probe and the cAFM probe have similar probe temperatures at the apex part when finding contact with the molecules. The thermal voltage

between sample and probe was amplified by high impedance differential pre-amplifier (SR551, Stanford Research Systems), and recorded by a computer.

Figure S31: Electric and thermoelectric properties of molecule **1**. (a) Aggregate conductance vs voltage histogram of electrical conductance vs. applied bias voltage by cAFM. (b) Measured thermal voltage vs. ΔT ($T_{\text{sample}} - T_{\text{probe}}$). (c) Linear curve fit of thermal voltage vs. ΔT .

Figure S32: Electric and thermoelectric properties of molecule **2**. (a) Aggregate conductance vs voltage histogram of electrical conductance vs. applied bias voltage by cAFM. (b) Measured thermal voltage vs. ΔT ($T_{\text{sample}} - T_{\text{probe}}$). (c) Linear curve fit of thermal voltage vs. ΔT .

Figure S33: Electric and thermoelectric properties of molecule **3**. (a) Aggregate conductance vs voltage histogram of electrical conductance vs. applied bias voltage by cAFM. (b) Measured thermal voltage vs. ΔT ($T_{\text{sample}} - T_{\text{probe}}$). (c) Linear curve fit of thermal voltage vs. ΔT .

Figure S34: Electric and thermoelectric properties of molecule **4**. (a) Aggregate conductance vs voltage histogram of electrical conductance vs. applied bias voltage by cAFM. (b) Measured thermal voltage vs. ΔT ($T_{\text{sample}} - T_{\text{probe}}$). (c) Linear curve fit of thermal voltage vs. ΔT .

Figure S35: (a) Electrical conductance distribution of SAMs **1-4** at low bias voltage (-20 mV to 20 mV) (b) Histogram of Seebeck coefficient distribution of SAMs **1-4**.

Figure S36: Comparison of the linear fit data used to extract the experimental thermopower values in Table 1. Black corresponds to molecule **1** and red to molecule **2**. This shows that at all measured temperature points, the thermal voltage of molecule **2** is higher than that of molecule **1**.

Figure S37: (a-d) Histograms of thermal voltage distribution of SAMs 1-4 at different temperature; (e-f) same as (a-d) but on a different sample prepared with same recipe, inset value the calculated Seebeck coefficient of different SAMs from the slope of the curve.

Table S5: Single molecule occupation area from QCM

	Δf (Hz)	m (ng)	Mw (g/mol)	A (\AA^2)
Molecule 1	104	90.7	471	33.9
Molecule 2	115	100.2	471	30.6
Molecule 3	99	86.3	444 ¹ /487 ²	34.2 ¹ /37.8 ²
Molecule 4	93	99.4	444/487	35.8/39.2

¹if SAMs terminated with SH

²if SAMs terminated with SAc

* A is the occupation area of a single molecule

Table S6: Single molecule occupation area from QCM

Figure S38 Representative QCM data sets for molecules 1-4 (a-d respectively)

4. References

1. Chanteau, S. H.; Tour, J. M., Synthesis of potential molecular electronic devices containing pyridine units. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2001**, *42* (17), 3057-3060.
2. Kaliginedi, V.; Moreno-García, P.; Valkenier, H.; Hong, W.; García-Suárez, V. M.; Buijter, P.; Otten, J. L. H.; Hummelen, J. C.; Lambert, C. J.; Wandlowski, T., Correlations between Molecular Structure and Single-Junction Conductance: A Case Study with Oligo(phenylene-ethynylene)-Type Wires. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134* (11), 5262-5275.
3. Lohr, A.; Swager, T. M., Stabilization of the nematic mesophase by a homogeneously dissolved conjugated polymer. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2010**, *20* (37), 8107-8111.
4. Wilson, L. E.; Hassenrück, C.; Winter, R. F.; White, A. J. P.; Albrecht, T.; Long, N. J., Functionalised Biferrocene Systems towards Molecular Electronics. *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* **2017**, *2017* (2), 496-504.

5. Nguyen, P.; Todd, S.; Van den Biggelaar, D.; Taylor, N. J.; Marder, T. B.; Wittmann, F.; Friend, R. H., Facile Route to Highly Fluorescent 9,10-Bis(p-R-phenylethynyl)anthracene Chromophores via Palladium-Copper Catalyzed Cross-Coupling. *Synlett* **1994**, 1994 (04), 299-301.
6. AXS, B. *SHELXTL v5.1*, Bruker AXS Madison, WI, 1998.
7. Sheldrick, G., Crystal structure refinement with SHELXL. *Acta Crystallographica Section C* **2015**, 71 (1), 3-8.
8. Soler, J. M.; Artacho, E.; Gale, J. D.; García, A.; Junquera, J.; Ordejón, P.; Sánchez-Portal, P., The SIESTA method for ab initio order- N materials simulation. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2002**, 14 (11), 2745.
9. Herrer, L.; Ismael, A.; Martín, S.; Milan, D. C.; Serrano, J. L.; Nichols, R. J.; Lambert, C.; Cea, P., Single molecule vs. large area design of molecular electronic devices incorporating an efficient 2-aminepyridine double anchoring group. *Nanoscale* **2019**, 11 (34), 15871-15880.
10. Artacho, E.; Anglada, E.; Diéguez, O.; Gale, J. D.; García, A.; Junquera, J.; Martín, R. M.; Ordejón, P.; Pruneda, J. M.; Sánchez-Portal, D.; Soler, J. M., The SIESTA method; developments and applicability. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **2008**, 20 (6), 064208.
11. Herrer, I. L.; Ismael, A. K.; Milán, D. C.; Vezzoli, A.; Martín, S.; González-Orive, A.; Grace, I.; Lambert, C.; Serrano, J. L.; Nichols, R. J.; Cea, P., Unconventional Single-Molecule Conductance Behavior for a New Heterocyclic Anchoring Group: Pyrazolyl. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* **2018**, 9 (18), 5364-5372.
12. Ismael, A. K.; Wang, K.; Vezzoli, A.; Al-Khaykanee, M. K.; Gallagher, H. E.; Grace, I. M.; Lambert, C. J.; Xu, B.; Nichols, R. J.; Higgins, S. J., Side-Group-Mediated Mechanical Conductance Switching in Molecular Junctions. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2017**, 56 (48), 15378-15382.
13. Yoshizawa, K.; Tada, T.; Staykov, A., Orbital views of the electron transport in molecular devices. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2008**, 130 (29), 9406-9413.
14. Li, X.; Staykov, A.; Yoshizawa, K., Orbital Views of the Electron Transport through Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons with Different Molecular Sizes and Edge Type Structures. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2010**, 114 (21), 9997-10003.
15. Tsuji, Y.; Staykov, A.; Yoshizawa, K., Orbital views of molecular conductance perturbed by anchor units. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **2011**, 133 (15), 5955-5965.
16. Hung, Y.-C.; Jiang, J.-C.; Chao, C.-Y.; Su, W.-F.; Lin, S.-T., Theoretical Study on the Correlation between Band Gap, Bandwidth, and Oscillator Strength in Fluorene-Based Donor-Acceptor Conjugated Copolymers. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B* **2009**, 113 (24), 8268-8277.
17. Lof, R. W.; van Veenendaal, M. A.; Jonkman, H. T.; Sawatzky, G. A., Band gap, excitons and Coulomb interactions of solid C60. *J. Electron. Spectrosc. Relat. Phenom.* **1995**, 72, 83-87.
18. Miao, R.; Xu, H.; Skripnik, M.; Cui, L.; Wang, K.; Pedersen, K. G. L.; Leijnse, M.; Pauly, F.; Wärnmark, K.; Meyhofer, E.; Reddy, P.; Linke, H., Influence of Quantum Interference on the Thermoelectric Properties of Molecular Junctions. *Nano letters* **2018**, 18 (9), 5666-5672.